

CAUSES OF ENERGY POVERTY AND ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL SITUATION IN SELECTED CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

Doç. Dr. **Ali KONAK**

Karabük Üniversitesi, İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi, İktisat Bölümü, Demir-Çelik Kampüsü,
Balıklarkayası Mevkii, 78100, Karabük, Türkiye
alikonak@karabuk.edu.tr

Toshkent Amaliy Fanlar Universiteti İqtisodiyot Bo'limi, Mirabad District,
Parvona Mahallah, Toshkent, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14899984>

SUMMARY

Energy poverty has become one of the most important issues of recent times. It is possible to say that there are many factors that cause energy poverty today. Some of these factors can be listed as inefficient use of energy, high energy production costs due to global problems and the reflection of these cost increases on prices, lack of sufficient energy resources in the country or difficulties in accessing energy resources and individuals not being able to access energy sufficiently due to decreases in real income levels. Evaluating the issue on a country basis can also lead to some mistakes. Because even if a country is considered a developed country, income distribution differences among individuals living in that country can cause energy poverty problems in that country. Energy poverty tends to be a major problem especially in countries where income distribution imbalances are high and the majority of the population has low income levels. Central Asian Turkish Republics have their own energy resources and their geographical locations make the energy of these countries more valuable. Because the Central Asian Turkic Republics are neighbors with China, which has made significant progress towards becoming a superpower, and this geographical proximity to China means a large market where they can sell their energy and therefore a large source of income for the Central Asian Turkic Republics. This study aims to evaluate the energy poverty of selected Central Asian Turkic Republics, which have significant amounts of oil, natural gas and renewable energy resources, in the period 2000-2022. As a result of the examinations, it was determined that as of 2022, energy poverty is an issue in Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, but energy poverty is not an issue in Turkmenistan, and energy poverty is not an issue in all selected Central Asian Countries in terms of access to electricity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid globalization process experienced in recent years has caused an increase in the need for energy. Especially due to the rapid developments in technology, there have been increases in both the production volume and the international trade volume with the development of transportation and communication channels. This has been effective in increasing the need for energy resources and energy factors. In addition, the globalization process has been effective in both changing consumption habits and increasing the consumption volume. Therefore, the need for energy is increasing day by day. In addition, energy is extremely important not only as an input of the production process but also as a directly consumed element and is used in significant amounts for this purpose. Within this scope, it is seen that energy is used intensively for lighting, heating, transportation and cooking. In this context, it is possible to say that the demand for energy, both in production and direct consumption, is at high levels. However, unfortunately, energy resources are limited on earth and it is difficult to meet the total energy demand. This causes increases in energy prices and the prices of almost all energy resources, especially fuel oil, are increasing day by day. When political tensions and wars between countries with energy resources are added to this, the prices of energy resources are increasing rapidly. In addition, the efficient use of energy resources is also extremely important. Because the inefficient use of limited energy resources, in other words, their waste, means both a loss of national income, causes the production volume to be negatively affected, and indirectly causes a situation that can be expressed as energy poverty. Energy poverty is one of the important research topics of the recent period. In its most general form, energy poverty can be expressed as the problems that individuals in some countries

and the entire society in some countries face due to their inability to access energy resources sufficiently in the process of meeting their basic energy needs. Energy poverty is encountered especially widely in developing countries and causes both the quality of life of individuals in these countries to decrease and negatively affects economic growth. Because the inadequate access to energy resources in both production and consumption processes causes the production activities to slow down and therefore the production volume to decline. On the other hand, developed countries have solved their energy problems to a great extent. This causes the gap between developed and developing countries to widen. In this context, it is possible to say that energy poverty has direct effects on economic growth. Therefore, the possibility and ease of access to energy resources is extremely important for both social and individual welfare increases. This study will analyze whether energy poverty is an issue in Central Asian countries, which have rich energy resources, especially in terms of oil and natural gas.

2. ENERGY POVERTY AND ITS ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE

Energy poverty is defined as the lack of access to sufficient, cheap, healthy, high-quality, safe and environmentally friendly energy services that support economic and human development (Emeç et al., 2015: 11). According to another definition, energy poverty is the lack of sufficient options in accessing sufficient, affordable, reliable, high-quality, safe and environmentally friendly energy services to support economic and human development. Difficulties in accessing energy also lead to differences in energy consumption among countries. Especially in underdeveloped or developing countries with high energy dependency, the issue of energy poverty is among the issues that are extremely important for the country's economy (Öztürk and Çelik, 2023: 48). In addition, energy poverty is also used to express situations where there is access to energy but this access is not sufficient and safe. In households that cannot meet their energy needs (heating, cooling, cooking, etc.) at a sufficient level for various reasons, there may be negative consequences affecting different areas of life such as health, education, psychology, and social life (Pehlivanoğlu and Yılmaz, 2022: 30). In addition, it is possible to express energy poverty as not being able to access modern energy opportunities. This situation can be seen not only in developing economies but also in developed economies and negatively affects well-being due to reasons such as low energy consumption and dirty or polluting fuel consumption. Access to energy is, first and foremost, a prerequisite for human development. The wealth and development of a nation are closely related to its citizens' access to energy and the type of transportation. For this reason, improving energy access opportunities is considered among the problems that governments must combat (Selçuk and Köktaş, 2018: 96).

Energy poverty directly affects economic growth and social welfare, first of all, and therefore its elimination is extremely important for economic development and development. Therefore, efforts to eliminate energy poverty are extremely important for the economic development and progress of countries. In other words, the issue of energy is at the center of many economic issues such as development, economic growth, poverty, unemployment, income distribution, production, export, etc. Access to energy is extremely important for countries to achieve their economic goals. While detailing the role of energy in supporting development, the International Energy Agency (IEA) observed that providing safe, affordable and modern energy for all citizens is at the center of poverty reduction and economic growth. Energy, one of the most important inputs of production, is more valuable for developed and developing country economies compared to other production elements (Öztürk and Çelik, 2023: 48). Therefore, it is useful to state that initiatives to eliminate energy poverty are extremely important. Beken and Lecuna (2023), in line with this idea, stated that investments made to solve energy poverty will support economic growth and therefore economic development in the long term. Today, two to three billion people - or roughly one in four people worldwide - lack access to the most basic energy services. In addition, consumers in the poorest countries also face high costs for energy services. Energy and energy poverty also play an important role in building an economically, socially and environmentally sustainable future. Providing reliable, safe and affordable energy services is of decisive and critical importance in addressing many of today's global development problems such as poverty, inequality, climate change, food security, health and education. Combating energy poverty has become a priority on the international

development agenda (Demir and Taşkın Kuveloğlu, 2023: 51). For these reasons, effectively combating energy poverty is extremely important in terms of achieving production increases, increasing export volume, reducing unemployment and eliminating poverty and ensuring social welfare.

3. CAUSES AND MEASUREMENT OF ENERGY POVERTY

Today, in underdeveloped and developing countries, there is a problem of not being able to physically access modern energy such as electricity, not being able to access lighting, cooking, space heating and cooling services, as well as not being able to afford energy services with the current income level. In other words, difficulties in accessing modern fuels, high fuel prices, inefficient use of energy due to poor building insulation, and income poverty constitute the main reasons underlying the current global energy problem and energy poverty (Demir and Taşkın Kuveloğlu, 2023: 53). However, there are also driving forces affecting energy poverty, and these driving forces consist of economic and political systems, climate, the state of the economy, household income, and the policy framework. These five driving forces, which directly or indirectly affect energy poverty, vary greatly from country to country and region to region. Economic and political systems can directly affect the development of the energy market and energy supply. Climate and climate changes have various effects on energy poverty. For example, in cold climates, the need for heating may be felt more, while in hot climates, the increase in cooling needs determines energy consumption needs. This situation directly affects the total energy demand in different regions as well as main variables such as building efficiency. The state of the economy and household income levels are also directly reflected in fuel use, energy prices and payments. The policy framework affects the level of support given to vulnerable consumers. (Öcal and Başarslan Arslan, 2022: 21-22).

Difficulties experienced in accessing modern fuels constitute one of the fundamental elements of energy poverty. However, access to energy creates employment opportunities, raises education standards, improves health status and thus helps ensure sustainable development (Uğur, 2023: 193). Individuals living in poor rural areas of developing countries in particular experience significant problems in accessing modern energy resources. Because investments to be made in these areas cannot meet the cost-benefit criterion and due to the lack of investment in these regions, individuals living in these areas cannot access modern energy resources. In addition, the lack of sufficient electricity and other energy networks in developing countries also makes access to modern energy resources difficult and causes energy poverty (Ateş and Atay Polat, 2023: 293-294).

Another important factor that causes energy poverty is high energy prices. At this point, the factors that cause energy prices to increase are of great importance. Especially in countries that are dependent on imported inputs, increases in exchange rates directly cause energy costs and prices to increase. In other words, increases in exchange rates increase the prices of energy resources that consumers directly use, such as fuel, and increase production costs by causing energy costs to increase (Solmaz, 2022: 391). In addition, with the gradual exit of global economies from quarantine measures, a significant increase in oil and natural gas demand has been observed, but for various reasons, energy supply has been insufficient to meet the general increase in demand, and this has caused increases in energy prices. When Russia's invasion of Ukraine is added to this, a sharp increase in oil and gas prices has occurred due to possible disruptions in supply, and the sanctions imposed on Russia and the embargo imposed on Russian oil have caused oil and gas prices to increase even more. Accordingly, energy costs have increased, electricity prices have increased, and the problem of energy poverty has deepened even further (Demirel and Tiğrek, 2024: 1520). In other words, price increases in energy resources make it difficult for individuals to access both products and energy resources, causing energy poverty.

Another important reason for energy poverty is the inefficient use of energy resources. Due to houses without thermal insulation, energy is lost and energy resources are used inefficiently. This means that more energy is spent or more is spent than the budget (Demir and Taşkın Kuveloğlu, 2023: 53). In addition, since energy systems have not yet been individualized, the amount of energy consumption and payments in houses cannot be controlled. In addition, energy prices increase with the privatization of the energy market, but despite the rising prices, the low energy efficiency of houses and household appliances and the fact that heating

systems are based on electrical energy increase energy consumption amounts and lead to energy poverty (Ateş and Atay Polat, 2023: 292).

Finally, low income levels also cause energy poverty. Because the decrease in individuals' real purchasing power causes their energy expenditures to decrease. In other words, individuals cannot meet their energy needs with the income they have. Although poor individuals in developed countries do not have a problem with accessing energy, they cannot meet their energy expenditures with their current income levels. The term inability to meet energy expenditures refers to individuals' inability to purchase the level and quality of energy required for their basic needs such as lighting, cooking, space heating and cooling, and using household appliances and information technologies with their income (Barış and Demir, 2023: 372). This is directly related to energy poverty. Because the problem of energy poverty occurs when an individual cannot benefit from the existing energy with their income.

Energy poverty can be measured with three different approaches that complement each other: technological threshold, physical threshold and economic threshold. While the technological threshold is based on the calculation of the population that cannot access modern energy services, according to the physical threshold approach, energy poverty is mentioned if the energy consumption of individuals is below the minimum amount of energy needed for basic needs. The economic threshold is based on the percentage of income that the household allocates from its budget for energy expenditures (Demir and Kuveloğlu, 2023: 53).

4. ENERGY POVERTY IN CENTRAL ASIAN TURKISH REPUBLICS

Each of the Central Asian Turkish Republics has its own energy resources. However, no matter how many energy resources a country has, its citizens may face the problem of energy poverty due to the reasons explained in detail above. In this study, which was prepared to determine whether energy poverty exists in the selected Central Asian Turkish Republics and if so, its level, access to electricity and access to clean fuels and cooking technologies were taken into account as indicators of energy poverty. An increase in the percentage of the population with access to electricity and the ratio of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies to the total population means a decrease in energy poverty. The data sets related to the variables were taken from the World Bank Development Indicators Database (WDI). The graphs, which are arranged separately for each country, show the access rates of the population living in the selected Central Asian Turkish Republics to electricity according to the technological threshold approach.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI).
<https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

In Tajikistan, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies increased from 36.1% in 2000 to 86.1% in 2022. On the other hand, the share of the population with access to clean fuels

and cooking technologies in urban areas increased in 2022 compared to 2000, and this rate, which was 78.1% in 2000, was 98.4% in 2022. In rural areas, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies has increased significantly in recent years, and this rate, which was only 20.5% in 2000, rose to 81.7% in 2022. When a comparative assessment is made between urban and rural areas, it is seen that the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 78.1% in urban areas in 2000, while this rate was only 20.5% in rural areas. On the other hand, the rate of access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in both urban and rural populations increased in 2022, reaching 98.4% in urban areas and 81.7% in rural areas. According to this data, as of 2022, only 13.9% of Tajikistan's total population, 1.6% of the urban population, and 18.3% of the rural population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies. According to this data, it is possible to say that there is energy poverty in Tajikistan in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies. However, as of 2022, Tajikistan's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies is above the world average in both general, urban, and rural areas. Because the world's average access to clean fuels and cooking technologies as of 2022 was 73.8% for the general population, 88.9% in urban areas, and 54.5% in rural areas.

In addition, the electricity access rate of Tajikistan's total population, which was 98.5% in 2000, has increased steadily since 2015 and reached 100% by 2022. A similar trend is valid for the population living in urban and rural areas. In this context, it is possible to say that there is no problem in Tajikistan regarding access to electricity for both the general urban and rural population, and therefore there is no energy poverty. In an environment where the average electricity access rate of the world population was 78.3% in 2000 and 91.3% in 2022, it is possible to say that Tajikistan's total population access to electricity is above the world average.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI). <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

In Uzbekistan, one of the most important countries in Central Asia, the rate of population accessing clean fuels and cooking technologies was 82.9% in 2000, while this rate decreased to 77.8% in 2022. In this context, it is possible to say that Uzbekistan is the only country among the Central Asian countries that has decreased in 2022 compared to 2000 in terms of the rate of population accessing clean fuels and cooking technologies. The share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas in the total population also decreased slightly in 2022 compared to 2000, and the rate, which was 98.2% in 2000, was 96.8% in 2022. In addition, there has been a very slight decrease in the share of the population with

access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in rural areas in recent years, and the rate, which was 71.5% in 2000, was 70.1% in 2022. When a comparative assessment is made between urban and rural areas, it is seen that while the rate of population having access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 98.2% in 2000, this rate was only 71.5% in rural areas. On the other hand, in 2022, the rate of population having access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 96.8%, while the rate of population having access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in rural areas was 70.1%. In other words, as of 2022, 22.2% of the total population of Uzbekistan, 3.2% of the urban population and 29.9% of the rural population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies, in other words, they are experiencing energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies. However, as of 2022, Uzbekistan's access rate to clean fuels and cooking technologies was above the world average in both general, urban and rural areas. Because the world's average access rate to clean fuels and cooking technologies is 73.8% for the general population, 88.9% in urban areas and 54.5% in rural areas as of 2022.

According to World Bank data, the electricity access rate of Uzbekistan's population, which was 99.6% in 2000, has been 99.9% to 100% for both the general population, urban population and rural population since 2016, in other words, it is possible to say that there is no problem in Uzbekistan regarding its population's access to electricity, and therefore there is no energy poverty. In an environment where the Average Electricity Access Rate of the world population was 78.3% in 2000 and 91.3% in 2022, it is possible to say that Uzbekistan's general population's access to electricity is above the world average.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI). <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

In Turkmenistan, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies increased from 99.3% in 2000 to 99.8% in 2021. The share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas in the total population remained unchanged in 2022 compared to 2000 and was 99.9%. In addition, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in rural areas has increased slightly in recent years, and the rate, which was 98.7% in 2000, rose to 99.5% in 2022. When a comparative assessment is made between urban and rural areas, it is seen that the rate of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 99.9% in 2000, while this

rate was only 98.7% in rural areas. On the other hand, the access rate of the population living in both urban and rural areas to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 99.9% in 2022. According to this data, as of 2022, only 0.2% of Turkmenistan's total population, 0.1% of the rural population and 0.1% of the urban population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies. According to this data, it is possible to say that energy poverty is almost non-existent in Turkmenistan in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, and in addition, as of 2022, Turkmenistan's access rate to clean fuels and cooking technologies was above the world average in both general, urban and rural areas. Because the world's average access rate to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 73.8% for the general population, 88.9% in urban areas and finally 54.5% in rural areas as of 2022.

In addition, the electricity access rate of Turkmenistan's population, which was 99.6% in 2000, has always been 100% from 2014 to 2022, except for 2019. In 2019, this rate was 99.9%. A similar trend is valid for the population living in urban and rural areas. In this context, it is possible to say that there is no problem in Turkmenistan regarding access to electricity for both the general urban and rural population, and therefore there is no energy poverty. In an environment where the Average Electricity Access Rate of the World Population was 78.3% for 2000 and 91.3% for 2022, it is possible to say that Turkmenistan's general population has access to electricity above the world average.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI).

<https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

In Kazakhstan, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies increased from 84.2% in 2000 to 93.1% in 2022. The share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas in the total population remained almost unchanged in 2022 compared to 2000, and this rate, which was 96.6% in 2000, was 97.4% in 2022. In addition, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in rural areas has increased significantly in recent years, and this rate, which was 67.9% in 2000, rose to 88.5% in 2022. When a comparative assessment is made between urban and rural areas, it is seen that the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 96.6% in 2000, while this rate was only 67.9% in rural areas. On the other hand, in 2022, the rate of population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 97.4%, while in rural areas, the rate of population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 88.5. In other words, as of 2022, 6.9% of Kazakhstan's total population, 11.50% of the rural population, and 2.60% of the urban population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies, in other words, they experience energy

poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies. In addition, as of 2022, Kazakhstan's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was above the world average in both general, urban, and rural areas. The world's average access to clean fuels and cooking technologies as of 2022 is 73.8% for the general population, 88.9% in urban areas, and 54.5% in rural areas.

It is possible to say that the electricity access rate of the Kazakhstan population, which was 99.6% in 2000, has been 100% for both the general population, the urban population and the rural population since 2005, in other words, there is no problem with the electricity access of the population in Kazakhstan, and therefore there is no energy poverty. In an environment where the average electricity access rate of the world population was 78.3% in 2000 and 91.3% in 2022, it is possible to say that the electricity access of the general population of Kazakhstan is above the world average.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI). <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

In Kyrgyzstan, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies increased from 51.9% in 2000 to 77.0% in 2022. The share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas in the total population increased in 2022 compared to 2000, and this rate, which was 84.2% in 2000, was 94.8% in 2022. In addition, the share of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in rural areas has also increased significantly in recent years, and this rate, which was 33.2% in 2000, rose to 66.4% in 2022. When a comparative assessment is made between urban and rural areas, it is seen that the rate of the population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 84.2% in 2000, while this rate was only 33.2% in rural areas. On the other hand, in 2022, the rate of population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies in urban areas was 94.8%, while in rural areas, the rate of population with access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 66.4%. In other words, as of 2022, 33% of Kyrgyzstan's total population, 5.2% of the urban population, and 33.6% of the rural population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies, in other words, they experience energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies. In addition, as of 2022, Kyrgyzstan's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was above the world average in both general, urban, and rural areas. The world's average access to clean fuels and cooking technologies as of 2022 is 73.8% for the general population, 88.9% in urban areas, and 54.5% in rural areas.

However, the electricity access rate of the Kyrgyz population, which was 99.6% in 2000, has maintained its high course over the years and has been realized as 99.7% as of 2022. In other words, it is possible to say that there is no problem in the Kyrgyz population's access to electricity, and therefore there is no energy poverty. In an environment where the average electricity access rate of the world population was 78.3% in 2000 and 91.3% in 2022, it is understood that the electricity access of the general population of Kyrgyzstan is above the world average.

Source: Prepared by me with the help of data obtained from World Development Indicators (WDI). <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators> (Access Date: 12.12.2024)

Finally, when we look at the world's energy poverty level, while the total population's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 49.2% in 2000, it has increased steadily over the years and reached 73.8% as of 2022. While the access rate of the population living in urban areas to clean fuels and cooking technologies was 76.1% in 2000, it has increased steadily over the years and reached 88.9% in 2022. Finally, the access rate of the population living in rural areas to clean fuels and cooking technologies has increased steadily, from 24.2% in 2000 to 54.5% in 2022. In other words, as of 2022, 26.2% of the world's total population, 23.9% of the urban population, and 45.5% of the rural population do not have access to clean fuels and cooking technologies, in other words, they experience energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies. This data shows us that the world's population's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies has continuously increased from 2000 to 2022, in other words, the world's energy poverty has decreased, but the energy poverty in question is still high.

While the world's population's access to electricity was 78.3% in 2000, it has increased steadily over the years and reached 91.3% as of 2022. The share of the population with access to electricity in urban areas in the total population has also increased steadily over the years and increased from 94.8% in 2000 to 97.6% as of 2022. The rate of access to electricity in rural areas has also increased steadily, rising from 66.5% in 2000 to 83.9% in 2022. In other words, as of 2022, 8.7% of the world's total population, 2.4% of the urban population, and 16.1% of the rural population do not have access to electricity, and therefore experience energy poverty. These data show us that the rate of access to electricity in the world's population has increased from 2000 to 2022, and therefore energy poverty has decreased, but energy poverty is still at high levels on a global scale. In addition, the share of the population with access to electricity in all Central Asian Turkish Republics in the total population in the 2000-2022 period was higher than the world average.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Energy poverty constitutes one of the important economic problems of the recent period. In its most general form, energy poverty, which is defined as the inability to provide sufficient, high-quality, cheap and safe energy resources, which constitute one of the basic elements of economic development, has significant effects on many macroeconomic elements, especially economic growth. Because one of the most important elements of the production process is energy. If energy cannot be provided at sufficient levels and quality, production activities will either slow down or stop, which will cause an increase in the unemployment rate, a decrease in the national income level, a decrease in the level of welfare and a slowdown in economic growth. In addition, the inability to provide sufficient energy will also cause decreases in the comfort of consumers. The reasons for energy poverty can be listed as difficulties in accessing modern fuels, high fuel prices, inefficient use of energy due to poor building insulation and income poverty. Energy poverty can be measured with three different approaches that complement each other: technological threshold, physical threshold and economic threshold. In this study, selected Central Asian countries were analyzed in terms of energy poverty level. As energy poverty indicators, access to electricity and access to clean fuels and cooking technologies data obtained from the World Bank Development Indicators Database (WDI) were taken into account. As a result of the examination, it was determined that in Tajikistan, there is energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, but there is no energy poverty in terms of access to electricity; in Uzbekistan, there is energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, but there is no problem in access to electricity, therefore there is no energy poverty; in Turkmenistan, there is no energy poverty in terms of both having clean fuels and cooking technologies and access to electricity; in Kazakhstan, there is energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, but there is no problem in access to electricity, therefore there is no energy poverty; and finally, in Kyrgyzstan, there is energy poverty in terms of having clean fuels and cooking technologies, but there is no problem in access to electricity, therefore there is no energy poverty. In addition, it has been determined that the world's population's access to clean fuels and cooking technologies and access to electricity has been continuously increasing from 2000 to 2022, in other words, the world's energy poverty has decreased, but the energy poverty in question is still at high levels. In line with all this data, it is possible to say that all of the selected Central Asian countries examined have both a clean fuels and cooking technologies and an access to electricity rate above the world average as of 2022. The fact that Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan have rich reserves of oil and natural gas, and Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan have significant renewable energy resources is of great importance in the emergence of such a result. Thanks to these energy resources, the energy poverty problem is either not experienced at all or is experienced at a limited level in these Central Asian Turkish Republics. However, this does not mean that the problem of energy poverty will not be experienced in these countries in the future. Therefore, it is of great importance to take serious and effective measures for the future. In line with this aim, investments in renewable energy sources should be emphasized, consumer awareness regarding energy consumption should be created, and existing energy resources should be used more effectively by developing technologies that will allow less energy to be used in the production process.

References:

1. Ateş, B. and Atay Polat, M. (2023). The effects of energy poverty and renewable energy use on environmental degradation. *Hitit Journal of Social Sciences*, 16(2), 290-315.
2. Barış, S., & Demir, D. (2023). Gelişmekte Olan Ülkelerde Gelir Eşitsizliği Enerji Yoksulluğunun Belirleyicisi mi?. *Journal of Emerging Economies and Policy*, 8(2), 371-384.
3. Beken, H. K. ve Lecuna, H.K.S. (2023). Türkiye'de Enerji Yoksulluğu ve Ekonomik Büyüme İle İlişkisi: Eş Bütünleşme Analizi, Yerelden Küresele Farklı Boyutlarıyla Enerji Ekonomisi: Güncel Araştırmalar ve Tartışmalar içinde (Ed. M. Zuhail), (pp.90-107), Bursa: Ekin Basım Yayın Dağıtım.
4. Demir, D., & Taşkın Kuveloğlu, D. (2023). Orta Asya Türk Cumhuriyetlerinde Enerji Yoksulluğu. *Uluslararası İktisadi Ve İdari Çalışmalar Dergisi*, 1(1), 50-70.

5. Demirel, İ. H. ve Tiğrek, Ş. (2024). Elektrik Piyasasında Kurumsal Yapı, Reformlar ve Yenilenebilir Enerji: Analiz ve Gelecek Perspektifleri. *Iğdır Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 14(4), 1512-1528.
6. Emeç, H., Altay, A., Aslanpay, E., Özdemir, M. (2015). Türkiye’de Enerji Yoksulluğu ve Enerji Tercihi Profili. *Finans Politik ve Ekonomik Yorumlar*(608), 9-21.
7. Köktaş, A., & Selçuk, İ. Ş. (2018). AB ve Türkiye’de Enerji Yoksulluğu. *Politik Ekonomik Kuram*, 2(2), 95-108.
8. Öcal, A. T., & Başarslan-arslan, T. (2022). Dünyada Enerji Yoksulluğuna Odaklanmak: Sorunlar ve Politikalar. *İnsan ve İnsan*, 9(33), 15-32.
9. Öztürk, Y. K. & Çelik, B. (2023), Yeni Sanayileşen Ülkelerde (N11) Enerji Yoksulluğu ve Ekonomik Büyüme İlişkisi, *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 64, 47-51.
10. Pehlivanoğlu, C. & Yılmaz, M. (2022). Enerji Yoksulluğu ve Covid-19 Salgını: Artan Eşitsizlikler ve Ülkeler Tarafından Alınan Önlemler . *İnsan ve Toplum Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi* , 11 (1) , 28-42.
11. Solmaz, M. (2022). 2002’den Covid-19 Pandemisine, Rus-Ukrayna Savaşına Türkiye Ekonomisinde Enflasyon. *Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Dergisi*, 6(2), 385-402.
12. Uğur, M. S. (2023). Türkiye’de Hanehalkı Enerji Yoksulluğunu Belirleyen Faktörler, *Enerji Ekonomisi: Teori ve Politikalar (içinde sf. 193-212)* Eds. C. Yardımcı ve Ş. Batbaylı, Bursa: Ekin Yayınevi.